

$p(e_i)p(e_j)=p(e_i+e_j)$ for Identical Photons the Basic Idea Behind the Bose-Einstein Distribution?

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The Maxwell-Boltzmann probability $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ may be obtained by starting with an a priori expression $N! / \text{Product over } i n(e_i)!$, then taking the \ln and using Stirling's formula. This is followed by an extremization subject to $\text{Sum over } i n(e_i) = N$ and $\text{Sum over } i e_i n(e_i) = E$. Alternatively, one may use reaction balance: $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ and $p(e_1)p(e_2)=p(e_3)p(e_4)$. We argue, however, that a more general idea is present, namely that $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l)$ because one cannot distinguish between any energy distribution for identical particles in the MB case. Here $p(e_i)$ is unnormalized. In other words, $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l)p(e_m)$ ((1)) if $e_i+e_j=e_k+e_l+e_m$. Basically, one can partition energy among identical particles in such a way that any partition has the same product of unnormalized probabilities as long as it represents the same energy. Thus, this is not simply a matter of two body collisions.

We extend this idea to that of photons in a gas with total energy E . In this case, there are photons with different frequencies ν_s (where s denotes the value of the frequency ν). We set $h=1$. These are considered distinguishable particles and we only apply the above probability ideas to identical particles/photons. The point, we argue, is that for ν_s , there will be some energy E_s and a number of cells N_s (which (1) computes). E_s is unknown, but if the principle ((1)) holds, one may distribute E_s in such a way that $p(r,s) = q_s \exp(-C r \nu_s)$, where r is the number of photons in a cell and ν_s the energy of a photon ($h=1$). Based on this basic idea, one may obtain the Bose-Einstein distribution for photons.

Distribution of E Among Identical Particles

The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ is often obtained in two ways. The first is the extremization of:

$$\ln \{ N! / \text{Product over } i n(e_i)! \} \text{ subject to } \text{Sum over } i n(e_i) = N \text{ and } \text{Sum over } i e_i n(e_i) = E \quad ((2))$$

The second approach is to consider two particle elastic scattering and reaction balance:

$$E_1+e_2 = e_3+e_4 \quad ((3a)) \text{ and } p(e_1)p(e_2)=p(e_3)p(e_4) \quad ((3b))$$

Taking \ln of ((3b)) and equating to $-1/T$ multiplied by ((3a)) yields $C \exp(-e_i/T)$.

We suggest that both of this approaches are really linked to the idea:

$$p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i+e_j) \quad ((4))$$

This means that $p(e_i)p(e_j)p(e_k) = p(e_l)p(e_m)$ if $e_i+e_j+e_k=e_l+e_m$ ((5)) Here $p(e_i)$ is unnormalized

((5)) is not linked to two body scattering. It is linked to distribution of energy among identical particles such that ((4)) and ((5)) hold etc. In other words, the unnormalized probability function is simply a math function which mimics the idea of conservation of energy, i.e. one may take an E and break it up into pieces of e_i such that the sum is E. With probability in the MB scheme, one uses $\ln(p(e_i))$ so that the summation is linked to a product of unnormalized probabilities. This scheme does not only hold in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, but also applies to a gas of photons, we argue.

Approach to Solving a Photon Gas Problem Given in (1)

In (1), an approach due to Bose is given. In such a case, a maximization of $\ln\{\text{Sum over } s \text{ } N_s! / \text{Product over } n(r,s)!\}$ subject to constraints on total E and N_s values is used. ($n(r,s)$ is defined shortly.)

Here we note that one does not know the total number of photons in the gas, but does know the total energy E. In addition, for each frequency ν_s (energy= $h\nu_s$ for a photon of ν_s , but we use $h=1$), one knows there are:

$N_s \text{ cells} = 8 \cdot 3.14 V \nu_s \nu_s d\nu_s \quad (c=1) \quad \text{phase space } V \text{ multiplied by spherical shell } ((6))$

((5)) gives the number of cells N_s for s , but one does not know how many photons of ν_s there are, only the number of cells. One may place 0, 1, 2, 3... numbers of photons in each cell. $n(r,s)$ represents the number of cells with r photons of type ν_s .

(1) obtains:

$n(r,s) = \exp(-(1+bs)) \exp(-d r \nu_s)$ where ν_s and d are Lagrange multipliers ((7))

d is a universal Lagrange multiplier while bs applies to type- s photon (i.e. ν_s).

The point we wish to make is that the basic idea from the MB distribution ((4)), ((5)) should apply to the photons of energy ν_s in N_s , even though one has no idea of the value of E_s (energy of type s photons) a priori. We argue that one could start with ((7)) a priori and write $\exp(-(1+bs)) = q_s$ where q_s is a function of s .

In other words, the basic statistical idea in this treatment is ((4)), ((5)) which applies to identical objects. It only applies to each ν_s , but does not apply to mixing of different ν_s photons even if the sum of energies is the same. Given this, one may use:

$N_s = 8 \cdot 3.14 V \nu_s \nu_s d\nu_s = \text{Sum over } r \text{ } n(r,s) \quad ((8)) \text{ and}$

$E = \text{Sum over } s \text{ } \text{Sum over } r \text{ } n(r,s) r \nu_s \quad ((9))$

The sum over r is linked to the form of a geometric series, i.e.

$$\text{Sum over } r=0, \text{ infinite } r \exp(-d r v_s) = d/d(-d v_s) 1/(1-\exp(-d v_s))$$

$$= \exp(-d v_s) / \{ [1-\exp(-d v_s)] [1-\exp(-d v_s)] \} \quad ((10))$$

The statistics is due to the distribution of E_s among $n(r,s)$, but summing over r removes r and if one uses ((9)), one sees weights due to different v_s (photon frequencies/energies).

$$\text{In particular, } N_s = \text{Sum over } r \ n(r,s) = q_s 1/[1-\exp(-d v_s)] \text{ or}$$

$$Q_s = N_s [1-\exp(-d v_s)] \text{ with } N_s \text{ given explicitly by ((8)).}$$

Thus, one $[1-\exp(-d v_s)]$ factor in the denominator is cancelled by $[1-\exp(-d v_s)]$ in q_s and one has:

$$1/(\exp(d v_s) - 1) \quad ((11))$$

(d is fixed using the constraint ((9)) as shown explicitly in (1).)

((11)) is the statistical factor distinguishing between different photon v_s energies, but it is really a result of the sum over r , which is linked with a distribution of E_s among $\text{Sum over } r \ n(r,s)$ photons of type v_s . The distribution is such that $n(r,s)$ is proportional to $\exp(-d r v_s)$, just as in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case. Thus, we argue that the root statistical idea is the same as in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case. If one considers distributions such as Kaniadakis or Tsallis cases, one no longer has ((4)), ((5)).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that there is a basic statistical idea behind the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, namely that one may take E and write it as $\text{Sum over } i \ e_i$. Here one may have any number of i . The idea is then to associate probabilities $p(e_i)$ with each e_i , such that $e_i = \ln(p(e_i))$ *constant for $p(e_i)$ unnormalized. In other words, $p(e_i)$ multiply while e_i 's add. We argue that this is the basic idea in the MB case and exists separately from an extremization of factorials subject to constraints or two body elastic scattering balance. We suggest that this idea holds for identical particles.

We apply this idea to a photon gas which contains different v_s (energy-frequency) photons and a total energy of E . One does not know how many photons are present, but for each v_s , there are N_s cells in phase space where N_s is a function of V (volume) and v . The idea is that for each N_s , one has an unknown E_s (because one does not know how many photons of v_s there are), but the principle of the above paragraph ((4)) ((5)) must apply. Thus, $n(r,s)$ = number of cells with r photons of type v must be of the form $q_s \exp(-d r v_s)$. From this idea, one may go on to use constraints: $N_s = \text{Sum over } r \ n(r,s)$ and $E = \text{Sum over } s \ \text{Sum over } r \ r v_s n(r,s)$. The $\exp(-d r v_s)$ form ultimately leads to geometric series and derivatives of geometric series results when

summing over r and ultimately yields: $1/(\exp(\beta \epsilon_r) - 1)$ as a weight for different photon energies ϵ_r , but it is really the sum over r and the principle ((4)), ((5)) which drives this result, we argue.

References

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